

It may be mentioned here that *cis*-caronic acid has been isolated in good yield by this method, the amount of *trans*-caronic acid formed simultaneously being very small.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Ethyl 2:2-Dimethylcyclopropane-1:1:1'-tricarboxylate (II).—Ethyl malonate (34 g.) was added in the cold to the solution obtained by dissolving sodium (5 g.) in absolute alcohol (70 c. c.). Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dibromo- $\beta\beta$ -dimethylpropionate (30 g.) was slowly added to the mixture and the reaction flask was cooled in a current of ice-cold water. When the addition of the dibromo ester was complete, the reaction was allowed to proceed under reflux on the water-bath for 3 hours. The alcohol was then distilled off as far as possible and the residual mass was treated with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried over calcium chloride and distilled in vacuum after removal of ether. After a considerable amount of malonic ester was distilled off, a colourless oil, which after repeated fractionation boils at $142\text{--}46^\circ/5$ mm., and at $153^\circ/9$ mm., was collected. [Found: C, 58.6; H, 7.9; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 280. $C_{14}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 58.7; H, 7.7 per cent. M. W., 286].

Alkaline Hydrolysis of (II): *Isolation of Caronic Acids* (III).—The above tricarboxylic ester (10 g.) was treated with alcoholic potash (10 g. in 100 c.c. of ethyl alcohol) and refluxed on a water-bath for 12 hours. Alcohol was then removed as far as possible and the residual mass treated with water. The alkaline solution was extracted with ether. The aqueous alkaline solution was then acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer on drying with anhydrous sodium sulphate and distillation left a residue which solidified on keeping. The whole of the residue was slowly heated to 200° during which carbon dioxide was eliminated. The mass was then treated with excess of aqueous ammonia and evaporated to dryness. The dried ammonium salt was extracted with alcohol leaving a small amount (A) insoluble in the solvent. The alcoholic solution was treated with ether and the precipitate collected, dissolved in water, acidified and extracted several times with ether. The ether solution on evaporation left a residue which when crystallised from water melted at 176° (*cis*-caronic acid, m. p. 176°). (Found: C, 52.96; H, 6.42. Calc. for $C_7H_{10}O_4$: C, 53.16; H, 6.33 per cent). The properties of synthetic *cis*-caronic acid are identical with those described by Bayer (*loc. cit.*) and Perkin and Thorpe (*loc. cit.*).

trans-Caronic Acid.—The insoluble portion (A) mentioned above was dissolved in water, the solution acidified with hydrochloric acid and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was then evaporated and the residue crystallised from water, m. p. 213°. (*trans-caronic acid*, m. p. 213°). (Found: C, 53.01; H, 6.47. Calc. for $C_7H_{10}O_4$: C, 53.16; H, 6.33 per cent).

Acid Hydrolysis of (II): Isolation of Terebic Acid (IV).—The tricarboxylic ester (5 g.) was boiled with hydrochloric acid (d 1.19, 30 c.c.) and the solution was evaporated to dryness. The residue was crystallised from water, m. p. 174°. [Found: C, 53.2; H, 6.4; Equiv. (in the cold), 156. $C_7H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 53.16; H, 6.3 per cent. Equiv., 158). The ammonium salt of this acid in alcohol cannot be precipitated by ether.

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on cis- and trans-Caronic Acids.—The acids were separately boiled with hydrochloric acid (d 1.19) and the resulting product was isolated as above. The acids melt at 174° and a mixture with terebic acid from the above experiment had the same m. p. A mixture of terebic acid obtained by these methods and caronic acid, however, melted at a lower temperature.

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PALIT RESEARCH LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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